

DEVELOPING AND DOING VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS SCALE FOR BEING NON-VOLUNTARINESS

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Abstract:

The main aims of this study is to define the validity and reliability for Turkish population “the Motivational Factors Scale for Being Non-voluntariness (Non-Voluntariness Scale (NVS))”, that questions why individuals who has never volunteered, participated any voluntary activity or has been volunteered before but doesn't continue his/her voluntary life due to problems he experienced, for Turkish population. In this study, sampling consisted of 138 participants who are living in Antalya city center and never been in any volunteer organizations or joined but not sustained being as volunteer has been applied and questionnaire form has been filled by face to face method. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was done, and was performed on 24 items for NVS and the NVS were grouped into seven factors. Whether the data was suitable to this analysis, Kaiser Mayer Olkin and Bartlett Spheritiy test results were taken into consideration and then, EFA was performed. Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency test was applied to the identified sub-factors and overall scale. Pearson Correlations Test was conducted to define the statistical correlation between sub-classes and items. In addition to this analysis, Confirmatory Factor Analysis method was performed and reached to satisfactory results in all fit indices. Results have been assessed according to significant level 0.01 and 0.05. As a result, it was founded that Cronbach's Alpha=0.894 and total explained variance= %71.179. It can be concluded that “the Motivational Factors Scale for being Non-volunteer has reliability and validity in the estimation of the non-volunteer motivational factors for the Turkish population.

Keywords: validity and reliability, motivational factors, non-volunteer

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1. The Concepts of Voluntariness and Being Non-volunteer

Helping others without expecting any outright has been advised institutionally by all of the religions as an indicator of good morality and it has been deemed/considered as a way of worshipping throughout all of the civilizations. When "Charity and Solidarity" has been considered as a value, its transformation into a behavior and manner of voluntariness is only possible by the existence and well processing of this value (Aktepe, 2014; UŞD, 2014). For this reason helpfulness is mostly caused by internal, and sometimes by external motivation. Because of this, all of the civilizations endeavor to raise their new generations keep this value alive. While helping can be a behavior that can be done by the individual himself, it is also an act that can also be done formally or informally with the people who have similar values as well. While the establishment of charity formally causes emerging non-governmental organizations which are called as NGOs, informal structuring is gathering individuals in an organized way in a channel by communicating in a way and making effort to achieve the determined mission (Ardahan, 2015). Even though charity and voluntariness are two different behaviors and manners, charity is one of the most elementary values that affect the creation of voluntariness (Clary et al, 1998). While charity is a behavior that is momentary and happens on its own, voluntariness is mostly a life style (Clary and Snyder, 1999).

Being non-volunteer is a two dimensional process. In the first dimension, the individual hasn't wanted to be a volunteer through his whole live and he has not become one. In the second dimension, however, the individual has been a volunteer in the past and gave up because of the negativity they experienced through the process of volunteering and from since, he has never wanted to be a volunteer in any way, shape or form.

Before explaining why individuals have not been volunteers, it is important to know why they have become volunteers and continued their voluntariness. While voluntariness has been defined as "*individual(s) taking a job over himself (themselves) in the society without expecting a reward*" in Turkish Dictionaryⁱⁱ; in SSDC (2006) it is explained as "*an individual's increasing the life quality of the people outside his immediate neighboring including his family and accomplishing a mission without any return and/or benefit expectation*", and in Ardahan (2015) voluntariness has been explained as "*individuals making an effort to create a positive change in the event that he/she intervened with the result in his/her/their free time, completely internally and taking as gospel, without any interest or benefit expectation, being forced and authorized by another person*". As voluntariness is explained in this way, involuntariness can be explained as "*an individual's not participating in any act as a volunteer, or giving up being a volunteer for some reasons and/or participating the events of voluntariness with an expectation of personal gain*". Not being lavisher and being non-volunteer should not be confused with each other. An individual can be lavisher and help without expecting something in return yet not put any effort into something as a volunteer. Alongside this, an individual may be neither lavisher nor volunteer.

ⁱⁱ - <http://www.turkcebilgi.com/gönüllü>, Okunma tarihi 23-06-2015

In the present day individualism and avoiding charitable acts towards strangers is a tendency that keeps increasing especially because of the increasingly challenging living standards of cities. Even individuals are in a life that makes them become increasingly insensitive and less keen on intervening negative events happening around them like in the saying: “let sleeping dogs lie”.

Either being an individual act or a structure established informally in some NGOs organized formally with others or in any channel, the theories used to explain the factors that motivate individuals for any behavior such as volunteerism, charity etc. may also be used to explain the factors that motivate individuals being non-volunteer in individual, NGOs or informal structure. In addition to Crandall’s theory (1980) which states that personality and the conditions in which the individuals in have influence, the factors that motivates individuals to be non-volunteer; these (factors) can be used to define the factors, as Levy (1979) defined, the structure that motivates individual to a behavior, the social values system formed by individuals’ personality and the social structure in which they are in and circumstances. In addition to this, being non-volunteer may be explained by using the Self-Determination Theory (STD) developed by Deci and Ryan (1985). In STD the process of motivation has been addressed in three extent; internal motivation, external motivation or anti-motivational/amotivational state. If there are internal or external motivational factors that cause an individual to become non-volunteer, the individual will not take himself/herself out of this process. For a person to become a volunteer he/she has to firmly support or be against an event or situation or he/she has to be in dissenting opinion. If an individual doesn’t have a strong supportive or opposite idea against an event, he/she won’t stimulate himself/herself when the event happens and the state of anti-motivation will continue and this situation may lead the individual to be non-volunteer. Alongside this The Achievement Goal Theory developed by Pintrich (2000) explains the factors that motivate individual as “Goal and mission-centered approach” and “Ego-centered approach”. While an Ego-centered approach defines being more competitive, Goal and mission-centered approach defines being helpful to others and being more focused on other people. Someone who has a competitive personality structure or someone that does not want helping others would prefer refraining from voluntariness. An indirect connection may be fictionalized between being non-volunteer and The Activity Theory developed by Engeström et al (2003). A person with a competitive spirit will always exercise and practice regularly in order to keep himself/herself in the competition, become successful and keep his/her mental, emotional and physical conditions sufficient. This increase of condition will trigger individualism and the individual will stray away from helping others and being a volunteer. Alongside this if the person does not identify or see being voluntary as a need, it will not be possible to explain this situation with Maslow's Need Theory transferred by Ibrahim and Cordes (2002).

When reviewed the literature, it is possible to come by many studies that question voluntariness through all dimensions. Although though they are not much, there are some studies that discuss the reasons that cause an individual to become non-

volunteer. Wymer et al (1996) discussed being non-volunteer, non-voluntariness and wanting to be voluntary yet not achieving it under the title of contextual limits in their study. Contextual limits comprised of reasons that identify why an individual wants to be voluntary yet cannot become one due to these factors and also why individuals may not continue the process of voluntariness. The person's not supporting that kind of a study due to lack of any voluntary association around him/her can be given as an example for these. In addition to the contextual limits, Clary et al (1994) have revealed one of the other reasons that prompt an individual become non-volunteer in their study. According to them, individuals not having enough free time may be counted in these contextual limits. Additionally Fischer and Schaffer (1993) have revealed that if the physical, mental and emotional conditions of a person are not enough to be volunteer, he would not want to be volunteer or if they are in the process of voluntariness somehow, they would not continue this. As another contextual reason, Rubin and Thorelli (1984) have stated that people will not be volunteers since they don't receive feedback after they have applied for voluntariness to organizations. In addition to the contextual reasons; beside the situation the person is in, personality and motivation theories, Ardahan (2011) discussed the factors that affect being non-volunteer and/or discontinuity of voluntariness as follows;

- The person does not want to take responsibility of any event, situation or another person,
- The person may not want to feel dependent, or committed to a place,
- Till that point nobody might have asked them if they want to voluntarily support them,
- The person may not believe that he/she has the capability to do something for that event or situation,
- In the current situation person has enough responsibilities,
- The person has not become voluntary due to a lack of self-confidence,
- The person may think that it would hinder his current job,
- The person does not have an understanding of "voluntariness" or that kind of a behavior does not exist in their families and traditions,
- He may beware that voluntariness may bring extra expenses and/or overestimate these expenses,
- He may have become volunteer once, and had bad experiences, his expectations fail to short, his work may have been belittled or left dustily,
- He may think that the voluntary acts are boring,
- The person's expectations haven't been in accord with the expectations of the organization, neither the organization nor the person has shown enough of an effort, therefore the person has been disappointed with voluntarism,
- The individual may have not been put in optimal position appropriate to his skills, talents and/or experience or he may not be supported by the organization that he volunteered. Even in addition to this, too many performance or jobs that exceed his capabilities may be asked.

- The responsibility level that the person has been voluntarily taken upon in the organization might be too little or too much than he wanted,
- Also the slow or poor management system of the organization in which the person volunteered might annoy the person,
- Beside these, the bad experiences the person had with other volunteers and the personnel of the organization may cause him to stop being a volunteer, or even worse leave all voluntary acts.

The purpose of this study was to define the validity and reliability for Turkish population “the Motivational Factors Scale for Being Non-voluntariness (Non-Voluntariness Scale (NVS))”, that questions why individuals who has never volunteered, participated any voluntary activity or has been volunteered before but doesn't continue his/her voluntary life due to problems he experienced, for Turkish population.

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

This is a descriptive study and it consists of people who have never participated in any voluntary activities or have been volunteered before but don't continue their voluntary lives due to problems they experienced.

2.2 Sampling Process, Data Collection Tool and Variables

The groundmass of this study consists of individuals who did not participate in any formal or informal voluntary acts through their lives with others. Sampling group of the study consists of 138 people resides are the city centre of Antalya and did not participate in any voluntary activities or volunteered before but don't continue their voluntary lives due to problems they experienced. As data collection tool, the questionnaire which is the specifically developed for this purpose was filled with the individuals face to face. Besides demographical information, total 24 items produced from the studies of Rubin and Thorelli (1984), Fischer and Schaffer (1993), Clary et al (1994), Wymer et al (1996) and Ardahan (2011) are given in the questionnaire developed. Five point Likert scale (1 - I definitely disagree,..., 5 - I definitely agree) has been used in the study.

To create validity and reliability of the model, explanatory factor analysis (EFA) has been made and sub-dimensions of NVS have been presented. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity results have been observed to look into EFA's applicability and since the results have seen statistically sufficient for EFA's applicability, EFA was applied and after the factor analysis, material-factor analysis was executed to test the structure validity. To look into the internal consistency of the scale, its Cronbach's Alpha parameters, and to check the connection between material and factors at the resulting scale Pearson Correlation Test were used and the results were questioned between significance level of 0.01 and 0.05.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) has been applied to NVS along with EFA and CFA Fit index values have been given in Table-4. As it can be seen in the table, fit index values statistically have good or perfect compatibility values/ adaptive values except one index (which is compatible/adaptive at an average level) (Sumer, 2000).

A total of 24 items have been asked in NVS questionnaire and since joint variances of all these items are over 0.50, they have been included in CFA. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value of the of the NVS scale which consists of 24 items that was given in Chart-1 is 0.816 and its scale value has been found above (0.6) as Kaiser (1974) has foreseen and its Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has been found as ($p < 0.05$). These results show that data on hand are suitable for factor analysis.

Varimax Rotation Technique has been used in EFA and factor loads and factorization results related to the scale have been given in Table-1. According to acquired factor divisions, the reasons that lead to an individual being non-volunteer individually or in an organization have been grouped into seven factors. The correlation values between factors and items have been given in Table-2. According to this factorization relations have happened correctly. In each group, the correlation values of that article are the highest in the group that factorized.

Total Cronbach's alpha value of NVS is 0,894. Obtained factors, the items ranked in the factors and returned eigenvalue (RE) have been found as follow;

1. **Insufficiency Belief and Negative Voluntariness Image** (DD=7.261; m11, m12, m13, m14, m15),
2. **Negative Voluntariness Experience** (DD=3.339; m21, m22, m23, m24),
3. **Not Knowing How to be Volunteer** (DD=1.582; m31, m32, m33, m34),
4. **Transportation Obstacle** (DD=1.328; m41, m42, m43, m44),
5. **Believing to be an Obstacle** (DD=1.270; m51, m52, m53),
6. **Lack of Time** (DD=1i205; m61, m62),
7. **Contextual Obstacles** (DD=1.087; m71, m72).

3. Findings/Results

EFA has been applied to test validity and reliability of the NVS that questions why individuals who has never volunteered, participated any voluntary activity or has been volunteered before but doesn't continue his/her voluntary life due to problems he experienced, for Turkish population and obtained results are shown in Table-1. As it can be seen from the table, EFA has been performed 24 items, Chi-Square = 1706.361, $p = 0.000$ and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (0.816) are found by performing Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. According to these results, it is seen that data set which is used is in accordance with the factor analysis. According to the results obtained with Varimax rotation method, 24 items are accumulated in seven factors by referring eigenvalues greater than 1 and 71.179% of the total variance are explained. Cronbach's Alpha value of the resulting scale has been found as (0.894). Factors obtained by EFA are named as follows:

F1: The factor named as “**Insufficiency Belief and Negative Voluntariness Image**” consists of the elements describing the negative images about volunteerism such as individuals’ finding their own skills and abilities inadequate, not relying on their own skills and abilities in order not to be a volunteer or continue volunteering. This structure consists the following items; “I don’t believe there is anything I can do”, “Negative sensations about volunteerism”, “Voluntary activities have been ignored around me”, “Voluntary activities have been belittled around me”, and “I do not have enough confidence to myself and my talents”. Cronbach’s Alpha value = 0.824.

F2: The factor called as “**Negative Voluntariness Experience**” consists of the elements describing past experiences and experienced problems that will negatively affect the individuals’ participating and/or continuing any voluntary activities. This structure consists on the following items; “Do not want to relive the negative behaviors when I volunteered”, “Believing voluntary efforts wasted”, “Believing volunteers mistreated”, and “Believing exploitation of efforts and labour of volunteers”. Cronbach’s Alpha value = 0.824.

Table 1: EFA Result

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.								0.816		
	Approx. Chi-Square							1706.361		
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df							276		
	Sig.							0.000		
Components Items and Factor Loadings										
Items	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	Communalities	M	SD
m11	0.423							0.502	2.221.11	
m12	0.642							0.670	2.221.04	
m13	0.762							0.683	2.301.09	
m14	0.841							0.783	2.281.13	
m15	0.722							0.629	2.321.21	
m21		0.737						0.719	2.431.13	
m22		0.725						0.734	2.421.13	
m23		0.771						0.697	2.311.18	
m24		0.831						0.729	2.671.35	
m31			0.889					0.877	2.521.24	
m32			0.869					0.851	2.571.27	
m33			0.700					0.697	2.631.31	
m34			0.463					0.521	2.631.20	
m41				0.680				0.706	2.731.30	
m42				0.779				0.750	2.701.35	
m43				0.853				0.803	2.771.45	
m44				0.728				0.675	2.751.41	
m51					0.718			0.649	2.831.17	
m52					0.710			0.622	2.801.13	
m53					0.734			0.744	2.571.13	
m61						0.792		0.728	3.021.36	
m62						0.860		0.793	3.361.23	
m71							0.833	0.761	2.221.25	
m72							0.751	0.760	2.151.20	
Cronbach's Alpha	0.824	0.853	0.834	0.845	0.736	0.733	0.654	For all scale		

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Rotated Eigenvalues	7.261	3.349	1.582	1.328	1.270	1.205	1.087	Cronbach's
Rotated variance (%)	12.522	12.207	11.856	11.719	8.639	7.454	6.781	Alpha= 0.894
Rotated cumulative variance (%)	12.522	24.730	36.586	48.304	56.944	64.398	71.179	

F3: The factor called as “**Not Knowing How to be Volunteer**” consists of the elements describing the individuals want to be volunteer but they don't know where to go, apply to be a volunteer and lack of the individuals who will lead them. This structure consists the following items; “Don't know where to apply to be a volunteer”, “Don't know how to be a volunteer”, “Lack of volunteers around me” and “My friends dislike participating these kinds of activities”. Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.834.

F4: The factor called as “**Transportation Obstacle**” consists of the elements describing transportation obstacles to participate and/or continue the individuals' in any voluntary activity. This factor consists of the following items; “Lack of opportunities close to home/work”, “My arrival/transportation to the place where I will participate in voluntary activities”, “Not owning my own car”, and “Lack of enough money for transportation”. Cronbach's Alpha value = 0,845.

F5: The factor called as “**Believing to be an Obstacle**” consists of the elements describing the individuals' participating in and/or continuing any voluntary activities would prevent their current work, school and social life. This factor consists of the following items; “The belief of voluntary activities would be an obstacle to my work/school”, “The belief of voluntary activities would be an obstacle to my current social life”, “Lack of a budget to be used for participating in volunteer activities”. Cronbach's alpha value = 0.736.

Table 2: Pearson Correlations between items and components

Items	Components Items and Factor Loadings						
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
m11	0.667**	0.375**	0.366**	0.272**	0.409**	0.036	0.383**
m12	0.761**	0.552**	0.199*	0.222**	0.258**	-0.096	0.324**
m13	0.810**	0.430**	0.174*	0.184*	0.347**	-0.129	0.158
m14	0.833**	0.479**	0.144	0.180*	0.351**	-0.072	0.154
m15	0.764**	0.450**	0.180*	0.249**	0.388**	0.058	0.266**
m21	0.593**	0.831**	0.232**	0.248**	0.284**	0.064	0.282**
m22	0.565**	0.836**	0.218*	0.247**	0.368**	0.169*	0.305**
m23	0.489**	0.846**	0.236**	0.260**	0.310**	0.082	0.271**
m24	0.366**	0.830**	0.150	0.127	0.313**	-0.019	0.206*
m31	0.197*	0.150	0.892**	0.432**	0.371**	.0260**	0.335**
m32	0.231**	0.186*	0.905**	0.461**	0.354**	0.308**	0.343**
m33	0.276**	0.200*	0.800**	0.562**	0.318**	0.276**	0.240**
m34	0.196*	0.274**	0.667**	0.380**	0.308**	0.298**	0.126
m41	0.242**	0.171*	0.554**	0.794**	0.288**	0.363**	0.318**
m42	0.240**	0.226**	0.484**	0.860**	0.303**	0.377**	0.308**
m43	0.233**	0.231**	0.465**	0.883**	0.342**	0.262**	0.224**
m44	0.242**	0.227**	0.370**	0.768**	0.382**	0.202*	0.301**
m51	0.361**	0.313**	0.359**	0.339**	0.794**	0.176*	0.215*
m52	0.412**	0.313**	0.227**	0.258**	0.808**	0.068	0.193*
m53	0.342**	0.298**	0.417**	0.371**	0.825**	0.003	0.253**

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m61	0.025	0.149	0.358**	0.362**	0.122	0.901**	0.240**
m62	-0.120	-0.009	0.259**	0.276**	0.059	0.877**	0.190*
m71	0.201*	0.153	0.200*	0.267**	0.183*	0.236**	0.868**
m72	0.378**	0.396**	0.357**	0.331**	0.289**	0.182*	0.856**

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01

F6: The factor called as “**Lack of Time**” consists of the elements describing the individuals’ not having enough free time to participate in and/or continue any voluntary activities. This factor consists of the following items; “Not having too much time” and “Having a busy work/business life”. Cronbach’s Alpha value is 0.733.

F7: The factor called as “**Contextual Obstacles**” consists of the elements describing the contextual obstacles that would prevent the individuals’ participating in and/or continuing any voluntary activities. This factor consists of the following items; “The presence of health problems” and “Being unhappy with the social environment”. Cronbach’s Alpha value = 0.654.

The reasons that motivate the individuals being non-volunteer and/or continuing volunteering are given in Table 2, the items correlation values with the factors are given in Table-3. As can be seen Table 3, even each item has a statistically significant correlation with other factors, it has the highest correlation value with the factor that belongs to.

CFA has been applied to NVS the model generated by factors obtained as a result of EFA, fit index values given in Table-4 have been obtained. As it can be seen in the table, fit index values statistically have good or perfect compatibility values/ adaptive values except one index (which is compatible/adaptive at an average level).

Table 3: NVS Factors and Items

F1- Insufficiency Belief and Negative Voluntariness Image

- m11- I don’t believe there is anything I can do
- m12- Negative sensations about volunteerism
- m13- Voluntary activities have been ignored around me
- m14- Voluntary activities have been belittled around me
- m15- I do not have enough confidence to myself and my talents

F2- Negative Voluntariness Experience

- m21- Do not want to relive the negative behaviours when I volunteered
- m22- Believing voluntary efforts wasted
- m23- Believing volunteers mistreated
- m24- Believing exploitation of efforts and labour of volunteers

F3- Not Knowing How to be Volunteer

- m31- Don’t know where to apply to be a volunteer
- m32- Don’t know how to be a volunteer
- m33- Lack of volunteers around me
- m34- My friends dislike participating these kind of activities

F4- Transportation Obstacle

- m41- Lack of opportunities close to home/work
- m42- My arrival/transportation to the place where I will participate in voluntary activities
- m43- Not having my own car
- m44- Lack of enough money for transportation

F5- Believing to be an Obstacle

- m51- The belief of voluntary activities would be an obstacle to my work/school
- m52- The belief of voluntary activities would be an obstacle to my current social life
- m53- Lack of a budget to be used for participating in volunteer activities

F6-Lack of Time

- m61- Not having too much time
- m62 - Having a busy work/business life".

F7- Contextual Obstacles

- m71- The presence of health problems
- m72- Being unhappy with the social environment

Table 4: CFA Fit Index Values

X²/ Ser. Der	= 343.81 / 231 = 1,49	SRMR	= 0.074
GFI	= 0.83	CFI	= 0.95
AGFI	= 0.78	NFI	= 0.89
RMSEA	= 0.060	NNFI	= 0.95
RMR	= 0.11	PGFI	= 0.64

4. Discussion

Testing validity and reliability of the Non-Voluntariness Scale (NVS), that questions why individuals who has never volunteered, participated any voluntary activity or has been volunteered before but doesn't continue his/her voluntary life due to problems he/she experienced, for Turkish population has been performed in this study.

It doesn't seem possible to explain why an individual become non-volunteer or continue volunteering with all motivation theories used to explain the factors that motivate individuals to become volunteer. If the individual doesn't accept being or continuing volunteer as a need somehow, it is not possible to explain any subdimension of seven subdimensions of NVS by Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs adapted by Ibrahim and Cordes (2002). But; how wanting something is possible and a need, not wanting is also possible and a need as well. For this reason if an individual sees being non-volunteer, it is possible to explain it with Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs.

Similarly, it is not possible to explain being non-volunteer and not continuing voluntariness with Ego-centered purpose and mission-centered objectives in The Achievement Goal Theory developed by Pintrich (2000). If the individual have a contestant blood or does not want to help someone, he won't be volunteer or if he somehow becomes volunteer, he won't continue voluntariness. In addition to these, if the individual does not prefer an active lifestyle, it is not possible to explain the elements in his life by The Activity Theory developed by Engeström et al (2003). Therefore, the factors in NVS cannot be explained by The Activity Theory. Beside this, the factors in NVS can be explained by internal/ endogenous motivational factors that form Self-Determination Theory (STD) developed by Deci and Ryan (1985). As the individuals' becoming non-volunteer may result from internal and external motivation, the individuals' giving up voluntariness who become a volunteer and giving up voluntariness somehow may also result from internal and external motivation. Also, it

is possible to explain being non-volunteer or continuing voluntariness with the amotivational state of the same theory.

It is possible to explain being non-volunteer or continuing volunteering by the presence of contextual obstacles mentioned in the studies of Wymer et al (1996). Moreover, the name of one of the seven factors of NVS includes the items that describe contextual obstacles. Besides while volunteering is an activity that performed and continued in free time, one of the most fundamental determinants of being non-volunteer may be lack of time or the person's current busy work. When viewed from this aspect, time constraint mentioned in the study carried by Clary et al (1994) coincides with "Time Obstacle" factor of NVS factors. Fischer and Schaffer (1993) described that the individual will not be volunteer since his physical, mental and emotional conditions would not be enough to be volunteer in their study. This coincides with contextual obstacles factor of NVS. The individual wants to be volunteer but doesn't know where he would apply or he applied to any NGO but he couldn't get any feedback. In their study, Rubin and Thorelli (1984) described this situation as individuals wouldn't be volunteer since he get any feedback after he applied to the organizations for voluntary and this is consistent with items of NVS. In addition to these, all expressions mentioned by Ardahan (2011) related to why individuals don't be volunteer and/or continue volunteering are ranked in NVS factors and coincide directly.

5. Result

After all this things told, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of NVS has been found as 0,894 and the variance announced by the scale has been found as 71,179% and , fit index values obtained by CFA has given a good and perfect fit with others except one index (there was a moderate fit as well). According to this, it can be concluded that the "Scale of Factors That Lead a Person Being Non-volunteer (Non-Voluntariness Scale (NVS))", that questions the individual's not becoming volunteer who has never volunteered in any stage of his life, hasn't participated in any voluntary activity or has been volunteered before but doesn't continue his/her voluntary life due to problems he experienced can be adequate to explain for Turkish population.

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